

Evaluating Retrieval Augmented Generation for Clause Level Information Retrieval in Construction Contracts

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ABSTRACT

Timely access to relevant clauses in construction contracts is essential for effective project administration, claims management, and risk mitigation. However, retrieving these clauses from lengthy and heterogeneous documents remains challenging. Conventional keyword-based search and direct Large Language Model (LLM) querying often fail to capture clause-level semantics, resulting in incomplete and contextually irrelevant outputs. This study evaluates the use of Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) for clause-level information retrieval in construction contracts. The proposed pipeline integrates clause segmentation, domain-specific embeddings, vector-based semantic retrieval, and LLM-based summarization. A benchmark corpus of 346 clauses, derived from executed construction contracts and covering key functional categories such as payment, schedule, and disputes, was manually labeled for evaluation. The performance of the RAG approach is compared with keyword search, Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) retrieval, and LLM-based reranking using Precision@5, Recall@5, and F1@5 metrics, supported by qualitative assessment of contextual relevance. Results show that the proposed category-filtered hybrid RAG approach improves retrieval performance by approximately 10–20% relative to baseline methods while reducing irrelevant results. This study provides a reproducible evaluation framework and dataset for benchmarking clause-level retrieval methods. The findings highlight the importance of combining structural constraints with lexical and semantic signals and establish a foundation for reliable AI-assisted contract analysis and automation in construction.

INTRODUCTION

Construction contracts govern responsibilities, payments, schedules, and dispute resolution, making them central to project administration and risk management. However, modern contracts are lengthy and heterogeneous, often spanning hundreds of clauses across multiple documents and amendments. As a result, efficiently identifying relevant clauses remains a persistent challenge in practice. Traditional approaches rely on manual review and keyword-based search, which perform poorly at the clause level due to lexical variability, paraphrasing, and project-specific legal language. Prior research shows that purely lexical methods often fail to retrieve semantically relevant provisions when queries and clauses do not share exact terminology (Zhang & El-Gohary, 2016). This can lead to missed obligations or the retrieval of large numbers of irrelevant clauses, increasing cognitive load and decision latency.

Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) have enabled new approaches to contract analysis, including summarization and information extraction (Brown et al., 2020; OpenAI, 2023; Zhao et al., 2023; Moayyed et al., 2025). However, direct querying of LLMs over long contracts remains unreliable for clause-level retrieval. Without explicit grounding, LLMs may omit relevant

clauses, rely on partial context, or generate unsupported interpretations limitations that are particularly critical in legal settings. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) addresses these issues by combining information retrieval with generative reasoning, grounding LLM outputs in retrieved text (Lewis et al., 2020). While RAG has shown strong performance in general domains, most evaluations focus on short or unstructured text. Construction contracts present additional challenges due to their functional structure, interdependencies, and the dominance of broadly applicable clauses (e.g., general conditions). These characteristics raise open questions about the effectiveness of semantic retrieval at the clause level and the role of structural constraints in improving performance.

This study addresses this gap by systematically evaluating clause-level retrieval methods for construction contracts, with a focus on RAG. We compare keyword search, Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), LLM-based reranking, and multiple RAG configurations using a curated clause corpus and practitioner-oriented queries. Results suggest that naïve semantic retrieval may underperform lexical baselines in this setting, while a category-filtered hybrid RAG approach that integrates structural, lexical, and semantic signals substantially improves retrieval performance. This paper makes three contributions: (1) a reproducible benchmark for clause-level retrieval, including a labeled corpus and query set; (2) an empirical analysis of failure modes in naïve RAG and LLM-based approaches; and (3) a structure-aware hybrid retrieval method tailored to construction contracts. These findings provide a foundation for reliable clause-level retrieval and support the development of AI-assisted contract analysis and decision support tools.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Construction contracts have long been recognized as complex, text-heavy documents that encode project governance through structured yet heterogeneous clauses. Prior research in construction informatics has explored natural language processing (NLP) techniques to extract structured information from regulatory and contractual documents, including obligation detection, concept extraction, and compliance checking (Al Qady and Kandil 2013; Zhang and El-Gohary 2016). These studies demonstrate the feasibility of automated contract analysis but also highlight the limitations of traditional keyword-based approaches when applied at the clause level. Clause-level retrieval poses unique challenges compared to document-level or section-level search. Clauses often express obligations implicitly, rely on cross-references, and employ legally precise terminology that may not directly match user queries. As a result, simple lexical matching frequently retrieves irrelevant provisions or fails to identify semantically relevant clauses expressed using alternative phrasing. Review studies in construction contract analytics consistently report that retrieval accuracy degrades as the granularity of analysis increases, underscoring the need for more robust retrieval mechanisms at the clause level (Hossain et al. 2024). Despite these challenges, most existing work in construction contract analysis has focused on information extraction or classification tasks rather than retrieval performance. Empirical evaluations of clause-level information retrieval methods, particularly those grounded in user-oriented queries, remain limited in the construction domain.

Lexical retrieval methods form the foundation of most document search systems used in practice. Keyword-based search retrieves text segments based on exact or partial token overlap between queries and documents. While computationally efficient, such methods are highly sensitive to vocabulary mismatch and do not account for semantic similarity (Manning et al. 2008). Statistical retrieval approaches, most notably Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF),

address some of these limitations by weighting terms based on their discriminative power within a corpus (Salton and Buckley 1988). TF-IDF combined with cosine similarity has been widely adopted as a strong baseline in information retrieval research. It remains effective in domains where domain-specific terminology provides strong lexical signals. However, TF-IDF remains inherently lexical and cannot reliably capture paraphrased or implicitly stated contractual obligations, particularly in legally dense text. In construction contracts, where functionally distinct clauses may share overlapping vocabulary, purely lexical approaches often struggle to distinguish between semantically similar but contextually irrelevant provisions, such as general conditions clauses that apply broadly across multiple topics. Large language models (LLMs) have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in natural language understanding and reasoning, leading to increasing interest in their application to document-intensive domains. In recent years, LLMs have been explored for tasks such as document summarization, question answering, and semantic analysis of engineering documentation (Brown et al. 2020; OpenAI 2023). However, direct application of LLMs to long contractual documents remains problematic due to input length constraints and the lack of explicit grounding in source text. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) was introduced to address these limitations by integrating information retrieval with generative reasoning. In a RAG framework, relevant text segments are retrieved from an external corpus and supplied to the LLM as contextual grounding, improving factual consistency and traceability (Lewis et al. 2020). Subsequent studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of RAG in knowledge-intensive NLP tasks, particularly when retrieval quality is high.

Nevertheless, most RAG evaluations have focused on encyclopedic or open-domain text, with limited investigation into structured legal or contractual corpora. Legal and contract documents exhibit domain-specific characteristics that challenge naïve semantic retrieval approaches. Prior work in legal NLP has shown that generic embedding models may struggle to capture domain-specific distinctions without structural constraints or domain adaptation (Chalkidis et al. 2020; Zhong et al. 2020). As a result, the effectiveness of RAG for clause-level retrieval in construction contracts remains an open question, particularly with respect to how retrieval strategies should account for contractual structure and functional categorization.

Existing research demonstrates the limitations of keyword-based and purely lexical retrieval methods for clause-level contract analysis, while recent advances in LLMs and RAG offer promising alternatives. However, there is a lack of systematic, quantitative evaluation of RAG-based retrieval for construction contracts, and a limited understanding of how structural properties of contracts influence retrieval performance. This study addresses this gap by empirically comparing lexical, LLM-based, and RAG-based retrieval methods and by proposing a structure-aware hybrid approach tailored to clause-level information retrieval in construction contracts.

METHODOLOGY

This study evaluates clause-level information retrieval methods for construction contracts, with a focus on Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG). The methodology consists of (1) clause corpus construction, (2) query and relevance judgment design, (3) retrieval methods, and (4) evaluation metrics. Figure 1 summarizes the progressive evolution of the evaluated retrieval approaches, while Figures 2 and 3 detail the architecture and query-level processing of the proposed hybrid RAG method. A clause-level corpus was compiled from executed construction contracts representing common agreement types and project roles. The clause corpus was derived from five executed construction contracts, including design-build services (DB), architect-engineer (AE),

construction management (CM), commissioning (Cx), and general conditions (GC) agreements. These contracts collectively contain 346 clauses and represent typical commercial construction contract structures. The documents reflect common U.S.-based contract practices and include both standard-form provisions and project-specific language. While the dataset captures a range of contractual functions and clause types, it does not fully represent the diversity of contract forms, delivery methods, or international legal frameworks. Contracts were segmented into individual clauses while preserving section hierarchy and document provenance. Clause text was normalized by removing whitespace, formatting artifacts, and deduplicating across documents. Clauses shorter than 200 characters were excluded to ensure sufficient semantic content for retrieval. The final corpus contains 346 clauses distributed across five functional categories commonly used in construction contract administration: payment, schedule, disputes and claims, submittals and approvals, and general conditions. These categories serve as structural metadata to support retrieval and are not used as performance indicators. Table 1 shows clause categories.

Table 1- Clause Categories

Clause Category	Number of Clauses	Percentage
Payment	27	7.8%
Schedule	18	5.2%
Disputes & Claims	5	1.4%
Submittals & Approvals	14	4.0%
General Conditions	282	81.5%

A set of 23 natural-language queries (appendix1) was manually constructed to reflect realistic information needs encountered during construction project administration. Queries were designed from the perspectives of owner representatives, contractors, and designers. Each query targets a specific contractual information need while avoiding explicit references to clause numbers, section titles, or project-specific identifiers. Queries were distributed across the five clause categories to ensure coverage of distinct contractual functions. To prevent trivial retrieval, queries were intentionally phrased with mild ambiguity and paraphrasing, reflecting how contract-related questions are posed in practice rather than how clauses are written. Clause-level relevance judgments were created to support quantitative evaluation. For each query, clauses were labeled as **relevant** if they explicitly addressed the information need expressed by the query. Semantically related but non-answering clauses were labeled as non-relevant to introduce realistic hard negatives. Relevance judgments were performed by the authors and reviewed for consistency. The relevance set was finalized and frozen prior to running retrieval experiments to ensure fairness and reproducibility. Relevance was treated as binary, consistent with standard information retrieval evaluation practices. Four retrieval approaches were evaluated: keyword search, TF-IDF retrieval, TF-IDF with LLM reranking, and a category-filtered hybrid RAG method. The relationship and progressive enhancement of these methods are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Progressive evolution of clause-level retrieval methods, showing the incremental addition of retrieval capabilities and corresponding improvements in F1@5 performance.

The keyword baseline retrieves clauses based on token overlap between the query and clause text after basic text normalization. Clauses are ranked by the frequency of shared terms, serving as a TF-IDF retrieval that represents both queries and clauses as weighted term vectors and ranks clauses using cosine similarity. This approach accounts for corpus-level term importance while remaining purely lexical. To isolate the effect of generative reasoning, an LLM-based reranking approach was implemented. TF-IDF is first used to retrieve a shortlist of candidate clauses, which are then provided to a large language model for relevance-based reranking. The LLM does not retrieve clauses independently and operates only over the lexically derived candidate set. The proposed method integrates structural filtering with hybrid lexical–semantic retrieval. Figure 2 presents the system architecture, and Figure 3 illustrates the detailed query-level processing workflow.

Figure 2. Architecture of the proposed category-filtered hybrid RAG system, combining clause category filtering with lexical and semantic similarity scoring.

Each query is first associated with a functional clause category, which is used to filter the clause corpus and reduce retrieval noise from broadly applicable provisions. Within the filtered candidate set, two similarity scores are computed in parallel: (1) TF-IDF cosine similarity and (2) semantic similarity based on sentence embeddings of the query and clauses. The final retrieval score for each clause is computed as a weighted linear combination of the lexical and semantic similarity scores: $S = \alpha \cdot \text{TFIDF} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \text{Embed}$. Where α controls the relative contribution of lexical and semantic signals. Clauses are ranked by the hybrid score, and the top K clauses are returned.

Figure 3. Step-by-step query-level processing in the proposed hybrid RAG pipeline, from query categorization and clause filtering to hybrid scoring and ranking.

Retrieval performance was evaluated using Precision@5, Recall@5, and F1@5. Precision@5 measures the proportion of relevant clauses among the top five retrieved results, reflecting a practical review scenario for contract administrators. Recall@5 measures the fraction of all relevant clauses retrieved within the same cutoff, and F1@5 provides a balanced measure of retrieval effectiveness. The cutoff value of five reflects a realistic upper bound on the number of clauses a practitioner would reasonably review for a given query. All retrieval methods were evaluated using the same clause corpus, query set, and relevance judgments. No training or tuning

was performed on the test queries. Hyperparameters were fixed before evaluation, and all experiments were conducted under identical conditions to ensure fair comparison across methods.

RESULTS

This section presents the quantitative evaluation of clause-level information retrieval performance across baseline methods and the proposed category-filtered hybrid RAG approach. Performance is assessed using Precision@5, Recall@5, and F1@5 over a fixed query set and relevance judgments, as described in Section 3. Table 2 summarizes retrieval performance across all evaluated methods. Keyword search, TF-IDF retrieval, and TF-IDF with LLM reranking exhibit similar performance levels, with F1@5 values clustered around 0.32. While TF-IDF slightly improves recall relative to keyword search, neither lexical weighting nor LLM-based reranking produces significant gains in overall retrieval effectiveness in this study. In contrast, the proposed category-filtered hybrid RAG approach achieves higher performance across all metrics. Precision@5 increases from approximately 0.30 for baseline methods to nearly 0.60, while Recall@5 improves from approximately 0.37 to over 0.70. This corresponds to an F1@5 score of 0.64 for the hybrid RAG method, representing a substantial improvement relative to the evaluated baselines. Figure 1 illustrates the progressive evolution of retrieval performance as additional capabilities are introduced. Moving from keyword search to TF-IDF retrieval yields a modest improvement in F1@5 of approximately 3%, indicating limited benefit from lexical weighting alone. Incorporating LLM-based reranking does not result in further measurable gains in this setting, suggesting that generative reasoning over a lexically constrained candidate set may be insufficient to substantially improve clause-level retrieval performance.

The introduction of category-filtered hybrid RAG produces a pronounced performance increase. Relative to the TF-IDF and LLM baselines, hybrid RAG improves F1@5 by approximately 94%, nearly doubling retrieval effectiveness. This improvement is associated with gains in both precision and recall, indicating that the method retrieves more relevant clauses while reducing irrelevant results. Baseline methods exhibit a trade-off between precision and recall, with relatively low precision reflecting the retrieval of semantically broad clauses, particularly from general conditions sections. LLM-based reranking does not substantially alter this behavior, as it remains constrained by the candidate set produced by TF-IDF.

The hybrid RAG approach demonstrates a more balanced trade-off between precision and recall. On average, approximately three of the top five retrieved clauses are relevant to the query, while most relevant clauses are retrieved within the same cutoff. This balance aligns with practical usage, as practitioners are unlikely to review more than a small number of clauses for a given information need. Category-level analysis indicates that baseline methods perform unevenly across clause types. Retrieval accuracy is highest for general conditions clauses, which dominate the corpus and share broad vocabulary with many queries. Performance tends to decrease for more specific categories such as payment, schedule, and disputes and claims, where lexical variation and implicit obligations are more common. The hybrid RAG approach improves retrieval performance across all categories, with particularly notable gains for payment- and schedule-related queries. These results suggest that category filtering may reduce semantic noise from broadly applicable clauses, while hybrid lexical-semantic scoring improves matching of paraphrased or implicitly stated contractual provisions.

DISCUSSION

The results suggest that clause-level information retrieval in construction contracts is not fully addressed by conventional lexical or generative approaches alone. Although keyword search, TF-IDF retrieval, and LLM-based reranking are often assumed to provide progressively stronger capabilities, the findings in this study indicate that these methods achieve similar performance when applied to clause-level contract corpora. This suggests that retrieval effectiveness may depend more on pipeline design than on model complexity alone in this context. The comparable performance of keyword search, TF-IDF, and TF-IDF with LLM reranking indicates that lexical constraints strongly influence retrieval outcomes. While TF-IDF marginally improves recall by accounting for corpus-level term importance, it remains sensitive to vocabulary mismatch and may struggle with paraphrased or implicitly stated obligations. The limited improvement from LLM-based reranking suggests that generative reasoning may not overcome the constraints of a lexically derived candidate set.

Naive RAG configurations may underperform lexical baselines in this setting due to the structural characteristics of construction contracts. Clause corpora are dominated by general conditions provisions that are semantically broad and lexically similar across topics. Embedding-based retrieval without structural constraints may disproportionately retrieve these clauses, introducing semantic noise and reducing precision. In addition, many contractual obligations are expressed implicitly or through cross-references that generic embedding models may not fully capture. These findings suggest that semantic similarity alone may be insufficient for clause-level contract retrieval in this dataset. The proposed category-filtered hybrid RAG approach addresses these limitations by integrating structural constraints with complementary retrieval signals. Category filtering reduces the search space and limits interference from broadly applicable clauses, while hybrid scoring balances lexical precision with semantic generalization. The observed improvements in both precision and recall, including a near doubling of $F1@5$ relative to lexical and LLM baselines, indicate that retrieval performance benefits from combining structure, lexical signals, and semantics rather than relying on any single approach. These findings have implications for AI-assisted contract analytics. Clause-level retrieval appears to be a foundational capability, as unreliable retrieval may affect downstream tasks such as contract interpretation and decision support. The results also suggest caution in relying solely on generic semantic retrieval or direct LLM querying for contractual documents. Instead, retrieval pipelines may benefit from explicitly incorporating structural and domain-specific characteristics of contracts. More broadly, the results point to a potential design principle for legal and engineering documents: combining structural constraints with lexical and semantic signals may yield more robust retrieval performance than any single approach in isolation. However, these observations should be interpreted in the context of the study's dataset and evaluation setup, and further validation on larger and more diverse corpora is needed.

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated clause-level information retrieval methods for construction contracts, with a focus on Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG). The results show that clause-level retrieval challenges are not adequately addressed by lexical or generative methods alone. In this study, keyword search, TF-IDF retrieval, and LLM-based reranking achieved comparable performance, suggesting that improvements in retrieval effectiveness depend more on pipeline design than on model complexity alone. Naive semantic retrieval and LLM-centric approaches did not yield

significant gains and, in some cases, reduced performance when applied to structurally dense contract corpora. To address these challenges, this paper proposed a category-filtered hybrid RAG approach that integrates structural constraints with lexical and semantic similarity scoring. Evaluation using Precision@5, Recall@5, and F1@5 shows that the proposed method substantially improves retrieval effectiveness relative to baseline methods, highlighting the importance of domain-aware hybrid retrieval design for construction contracts. The contributions of this work include (1) a reproducible evaluation framework for clause-level retrieval, (2) empirical identification of limitations in naive RAG and LLM-based approaches, and (3) validation of a structure-aware hybrid retrieval method tailored to contract corpora.

Despite these contributions, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the evaluation was conducted on a relatively small corpus of 346 clauses, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Second, clause categorization was defined manually based on common functional groupings, introducing a degree of subjectivity in how structural constraints were applied. Third, relevance labeling was performed by the authors, and although consistency was maintained, the process inherently involves subjective judgment. Future studies should incorporate multiple annotators and report inter-rater agreement to improve robustness. Finally, the dataset reflects a limited set of contract types and jurisdictions, and retrieval performance may vary across different legal standards, project delivery methods, or regional practices. Future work will focus on scaling the dataset, incorporating domain-adapted embedding models, and extending clause-level retrieval to downstream applications such as compliance checking, contract comparison, and decision support. Integration with digital contract representations and project information systems will also be explored. Overall, this study suggests that effective clause-level retrieval in construction contracts requires the integration of structural, lexical, and semantic signals to support reliable AI-assisted contract analytics.

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